

THE USE OF STEEL WIRES TO IMPROVE THE TOUGHNESS OF

CARBON FIBRE-RESIN COMPOSITES

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Abstract

As a measure to prevent catastrophic damage to components fabricated from carbon fibre reinforced resins when they are subjected to impact loads, additions of a low volume fraction of high tensile steel wires were made to mouldings. Preliminary investigations indicated that this kind of approach could help because some residual load bearing capacity was maintained after the impact blow. High carbon, cold drawn steel wires with diameters ranging from 0.13 to 0.26 mm were incorporated in a resin composite unidirectionally reinforced with ~0.49 Vf Type III untreated carbon fibres. The interlaminar shear strength was unaltered by the presence of the wires and small increases were found in the flexural strength. Increases of ~50% were found in the impact values obtained normal to the test panel surface and close to 100% for the transverse direction. Notched slow bend tests gave energy absorption values of the same order as those provided by the impact tests. It was revealed that the carbon fibre-resin samples without wires failed completely with cracks initiating and propagating from opposite surfaces subjected to tensile and compressive stresses. The inclusion of the steel wires prevented complete specimen separation and virtually excluded the compressive type of failure. The increases in energy absorption which have been measured in the steel containing composites may be accounted for by delamination, fibre and wire pull out, as well as local plastic deformation of the wire.

1.0 Introduction

During the past five years a great deal of effort⁽¹⁻⁶⁾ has been expended in determining and providing an explanation of the fracture properties of carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites. Linear fracture mechanics approaches and more simple pendulum impact tests have been employed, usually producing comparable data. The resistance to fracture of these materials particularly under the action of impact loading has been shown to depend on the strength, modulus and volume fraction of the fibres together with the magnitude of the shear strength of the fibre-matrix interface. Assuming that adequate care has been taken in composite preparation such properties are dependant on fibre processing variables e.g. final treatment temperature and the nature of the surface treatment. Bader et al⁽⁴⁾ have examined the form of the load-deflection plots produced in an instrumented impact test together with the broken specimens and have concluded that three failure mechanisms are possible: (a) fast brittle crack propagation (minimum energy), (b) stepwise reduction of the section (intermediate energy) and (c) multiple shear in which failure parallel to the fibre axis occurs on a wide scale (maximum energy). Hence, weakly bonded composites with low inter-laminar shear strengths prepared from non-surface treated fibres of low modulus usually have the better impact properties. Unfortunately, such composites do not possess satisfactory transverse and shear strength values for engineering usage.

On the basis of some initial investigations by Baker⁽⁷⁾ attempts have been made by the present authors to examine a means of introducing additional resistance to fracture under impact loading conditions whilst maintaining shear and transverse properties. The approach involves the incorporation of a secondary reinforcing fibre of similar strength and modulus to carbon together with added attraction of a small plastic yield before final failure. Such a yield would be expected to take place at the failure strain of the carbon fibre thus raising the effective fracture energy of the composite. Hard drawn, high carbon steel wire of diameter ~ 0.2 mm, has been used here at small volume fractions ($\sim 0.1 V_f^S$) to test these suppositions. It may be noted that the added volume of steel should not provide a significant weight penalty for this high specific strength material, e.g. the addition of steel wire to a V_f^S of 0.08 to a $0.60 V_f^C$ carbon fibre composite will raise the specific gravity from 1.7 to 2.

The evaluation described in subsequent sections centres on an assessment of the effect of the steel wires on the flexural, shear and impact properties of C.F.R.P.

2.0 Materials

Composite test panels of the basic C.F.R.P. and of the wire reinforced material were fabricated from commercially available prepreg sheet. The sheet had been prepared from type III untreated carbon fibres impregnated with partially cured HR4C resin (the resin is a mechanical dispersion of an epoxy and polysulphone). The mechanical properties of the carbon fibres used for this batch of material as provided by the manufacturers are given in Table I.

Two different types of wire have been used as second phase fibre reinforcing materials, both hard drawn high carbon steels which are commercially available, i.e. a piano wire (0.13 and 0.26 mm diameter) and a higher strength wire known as "Rocket" wire (0.13 mm diameter). The tensile properties of these wires are given in Table I.

The introduction of the steel wires into the composite was accomplished by a lathe-winding process. Sheets of carbon fibre prepreg were taped on either side of a flat paddle which was secured in the chuck of a lathe. Wire supplied from a reel via a pretensioning device was attached to a retaining screw on the paddle and then wound over the carbon fibre prepreg sheets at a low speed. The wire spacing was calculated to give a $0.08 V_f^S$ of wire in the pressed composite.

After removing the paddle from the lathe, sheets of resin mounted on backing paper were ironed onto the paddle leaving a sheet of resin over and between the wires. Finally another sheet of carbon fibre prepreg was ironed over the wires. After the prepreg-wire-prepreg sandwich had been removed from the paddle, care was taken to keep it flat by storing on a level surface under an evenly applied load.

Sandwiches were cut to the test panel size of 200 mm x 75 mm and layed up in a mould preheated to 165°C. Eight sandwiches were required to produce a final mould thickness of 2.5 mm. The panel was formed under 'leaky' mould conditions at a pressure of 3.4 MN/m² to fixed stops at a temperature of 160 ± 5°C for 1 h. After this period, the panel was removed from the mould and post-cured for 2 h at 180°C. At least two panels of each type of material were prepared to assess panel to panel variations that might result from processing.

3.0 Experimental Procedure and Results

3.1 Microstructural examination

Transverse sections cut from the test panels were mounted and polished for microscopic examination using conventional

techniques. Typical microstructures are shown in Figure 1. Sound, void free samples were observed with a good distribution of wires. There was some tendency toward clustering with the coarser wires. The wires tended to be surrounded by carbon free resin areas, presumably due to the incorporation of excess resin sheets which were not entirely excluded during the pressing operation. Quantitative analysis of the samples was carried out on a "Quantimet" Image Analysing Computer and the overall volume fractions of the components in the test panels are given in Table II. The total volume fractions of reinforcing fibres in the composites containing steel and carbon are seen to remain reasonably constant.

3.2 Short beam interlaminar shear strength

The short beam interlaminar shear strength (I.L.S.S.) tests were undertaken using a three point bend fixture with a 6.4 mm diameter roller in either an Instron or servo-hydraulic test frame. Samples of nominal dimensions 16.5 mm x 6.4 mm x 2.5 mm were cut from the test panel with the 16.5 mm dimension parallel to the fibre direction using a diamond cutting wheel in a surface grinding machine. The samples were tested over a span such that the span-to-depth (L/d) ratio was maintained at 5. The mean values obtained from between 20 and 30 duplicate tests are given in Table II. There is no apparent effect on this property through introducing wires into the basic carbon-resin composite. The I.L.S.S. values measured on these composites are slightly above those⁽⁴⁾ found in composites containing non-surface treated carbon fibres of low modulus.

3.3 Flexural strength

The flexural strength was determined using specimens of dimension 125 mm x 6.4 mm x 2.5 mm tested in three point bending over a span of 100 mm i.e. a L/d value of ~40. The results of ~15 tests per material are given in Table II. A small increase is found in the mean values of the flexural strength in the wire reinforced specimens, but the increase lies well within the scatter obtained and so it may be concluded that the wire has little effect on the magnitude of this property. The flexural strength of the straight HR4C represents ~97% of the 'rule of mixtures' value calculated from the data given in Table I and assuming a polymer resin strength of ~100 MN/m² at the failure strain.

However, it was noted that the presence of the wires changed the type of failure that occurred in these materials. During testing, the critical failure which destroyed the load bearing capacity of the beam was a failure initiated at the compressive surface in all the plain and some of the wire reinforced specimens. In the plain specimens no tensile failure occurred

until compressive failure was initiated and both types then appeared to occur simultaneously with complete specimen separation. In the wire reinforced material small amounts of tensile failure were observed initially as bundles of fibres broke and some local delamination occurred. This did not seriously affect the load carrying capacity of the beam. One of two processes could then occur, either compressive failure resulting in the loss of all load bearing capacity, or a continuation of the tensile failure and the delamination process. In the latter case, the beam thickness was progressively reduced until only a thin ligament of unbroken material remained. In no case, irrespective of the fracture sequence, did the wires fail completely. Hence the wire-reinforced specimens retained a measure of residual strength which was not found in the plain specimens.

3.4 Impact tests

Impact testing was carried out using a miniature Charpy plastics impact testing machine. The machine is designed to take a series of penduli which strike the specimen at a velocity of 2.4 m/s. For this series of tests either a 1.35 J or a 2.71 J pendulum was used. The specimens, of dimensions 50 mm x 2.5 mm x 2.5 mm, were unnotched and broken over a span of 38 mm in two directions, (i) normal to the panel surface (designated normal), and (ii) normal to the panel edge (designated transverse). The energy absorbed by impact was divided by the cross-sectional area and the resulting fracture energy given in the units kJ/m^2 . The mean values obtained are given in Table II and Figure 2. The only specimens which completely separated at the point of impact were those carried out on the transverse plain HR4C composites and these have the lowest impact values recorded. All the others, including the wire containing specimens in the transverse direction, showed various degrees of delamination and often failed in a multiple shear mode, that is shearing longitudinally into several pieces.

Photographs of a selection of failed specimens are shown in Figure 3. The specimen shown in Figure 3(a) is typical of a failure of the plain composite, with tensile and compressive failures initiating from opposite surfaces, and local delamination at the middle of the section. The photographs, Figure 3(b-d), are all of wire reinforced composite and show the varying degrees of delamination which can occur. It was noted that the energy absorbed during impact increases with the degree of delamination. While in most cases there has been some compressive damage, this is almost exclusively surface damage, probably as the compressive crack has been arrested on its first encounter with the steel wires.

3.5 Slow bend fracture tests

Slow bend fracture tests, after the manner of Tattersall and Tappin⁽⁸⁾ were carried out with a three-point bend over a span of 38 mm. The specimens of dimensions 50 mm x 2.5 mm x 2.5 mm were tested at a cross-head speed of 5 mm/min in an Instron machine. The energy absorbed was calculated from planimeter measurements of the area under the load-displacement curve. In some cases complete failure did not occur because the crack was deflected by delamination. Hence, the energy to either failure or 5 mm displacement was measured, whichever occurred first. The errors involved in measuring the energy up to a 5 mm displacement only imposed a small error because the load had dropped to a very low level at the limiting displacement, i.e. ~5% of the maximum load. The work to fracture in kJ/m^2 is found by dividing the energy value from the curves by the cross-sectional area of the triangular section.

The results of the tests are shown in Figure 4 where each point represents an experimental result. Comparison of these energy values with impact results shown in Table II indicates that the straight HR4C material has a smaller transverse value but the slow bend result for the normal sample is ~20% below that of its equivalent impact value. As can be seen there is a large scatter in the results in both the normal and transverse directions for the steel wire samples and this makes direct numerical comparisons between impact and slow bend values difficult. Further examination of the load-deflection plots for the steel wire containing samples did show different patterns of failure, see Figure 5, despite the fact that a consistent maximum load was registered. In the case of plot (a) a small number of large load drops were observed with relatively few instances of load recovery. Plot (b) shows a larger number of small vertical drops and again few instances of load recovery. Whilst in plot (c) a maximum number of small load drops are interspersed with frequent load recovery regions. The energy absorbed obviously increases from plot (a) to (b) to (c).

Visual inspection of the failed specimens in general showed that three distinct types of failure occurred. The first type showed tensile failure initiating at the tip of the notch with the tensile crack propagating slowly through the specimen. At some point a compressive crack initiated and this propagated at a high speed through the unbroken portion of the specimen. In the wire containing specimens this did not cause complete separation as the wires bridging the compressive crack had not failed. Failures of this type showed the lowest energy absorbing capacity and possessed a load-deflection plot of type (a) in Figure 5.

The second type, which was of intermediate energy absorbing

capacity, exhibited complete tensile failure, the tensile crack initiating at the notch tip and progressing slowly throughout the specimen, plot type (b) (Figure 5). The highest energy absorbing failure occurred when delamination of the specimen took place, that is when the tensile crack was not sufficiently constrained to run in the plane of the notch, but was diverted in the fibre direction. When this occurred a ligament of unbroken material remained at the base of the notch, plot type (c) (Figure 5). Figure 6 shows photographs of specimens which exhibited compressive failure, and which delaminated leaving an unbroken ligament. In addition, Figure 7, illustrates combinations of tensile and compressive failures in samples with and without wire reinforcement.

4.0 Discussion

The data obtained in the I.L.S.S. and flexural strength tests indicated that the introduction $0.08 V_f^S$ of steel wire into carbon-polymer resin composites had not significantly altered these properties. In the case of the wire containing samples there is some slight suggestion that the strength has increased as a result of their inclusion. The measurements of shear stress by the short beam test have been criticised⁽⁴⁾ on a number of grounds, nevertheless, the results can be used in a comparative way to show that the resin-wire bond strength is at least as good as that of the resin-carbon fibre interface.

4.1 Failure modes in flexural strength tests

It was noticeable that the onset of compressive failure was retarded in the wire containing specimens, whilst this failure mechanism was almost always associated with the samples reinforced with just carbon. Such observations may be understood if note is taken of the fact that the wires should have superior resistance to a buckling failure when compared with carbon fibres, i.e. because of their greater diameter and ductility. An extension of this argument would suggest that the coarser 0.26 mm wire would be more resistant to buckling and therefore to a compressive type of failure when included in a composite than the 0.13 mm diameter material. However, there is no evidence for suggesting that the frequency of complete suppression of compressive failure was any greater in the composites containing the coarser wires. It must be stated that for a given volume fraction of wire, the number of 0.26 mm wires per unit area in the composite is only one quarter of the number of 0.13 mm wires, hence the greater stability in buckling of the coarser wires may be compensated for by the greater number of fine wires. This discussion does not detract from the conclusion that the addition of wires, no matter what the mode of failure, prevented complete separation of the test piece and gave it a measure of residual strength, due to unfailed wires alone, or both unfailed wires

and carbon fibres.

4.2 Evaluation of fracture tests

It is clear from the impact tests that energy absorbed during failure is significantly raised by the wire i.e. in the normal mode of testing from 40% up to 70% and in the transverse mode from 63% to 88%. Comparison of the impact with the slow bend data does present some problems. For instance with the impact results there is a difference in the energy levels absorbed between those obtained on samples tested in the normal direction and those in the transverse direction of between 35 and 56 kJ/m²; whilst the slow bend tests show some degree of overlap and scatter. The question of whether the two types of test are measuring the same physical processes can be answered from an examination of the failure modes.

In the transverse impact test and in some normal and transverse slow bend tests on the plain HR4C material the manner of failure was identical, predominantly compressive buckling failure with some degree of tensile pullout and no delamination. The numerical value of energy absorbed is almost identical.

Compressive failure was virtually eliminated in the wire reinforced samples subjected to impact but was still observed in a proportion of slow bend test samples in both normal and transverse directions. A larger amount of delamination was observed in the normal impact tests of wire containing composites than when the same material was tested in the transverse direction. In the slow bend tests of those samples which did not show compressive failure a small amount of delamination was observed. Hence, the transverse impact results, with a predominantly tensile pullout failure with a small amount of delamination but no compressive failure, should compare with the slow bend result from specimens that did not fail compressively. This can be seen to be correct, see Table II and Figure 4. The slow bend results obtained on any kind of sample do not seriously overlap the high values found for the normal impact tests on wire reinforced material. This can be adequately explained by the observation of gross amounts of multiple shear in the latter type of test.

While the wires appear to control the type of failure, there must be some increment of energy due to plastic deformation of the wire itself. Assuming the wire fails totally the energy absorbed per unit area can be calculated from,

$$\text{Energy/unit area} = \Delta l_o \epsilon^F \sigma_f^F V_f \dots (1)$$

where Δl is the total length of necked wire,
 ϵ_f^0 is the wire failure strain
 σ_f is the wire failure stress
 V_f is the wire volume fraction.

The calculated values for the wires used in the present experiments are:

0.13 mm piano	10.7 kJ/m ²
0.26 mm piano	9.4 kJ/m ²
0.13 mm Rocket	20.7 kJ/m ²

Since these figures relate to wire failure and thus total specimen separation, they are maximum values that could be absorbed. It is clear that plastic deformation does occur in these failures, see Figure 8, but the energy consumed cannot account for the increase in impact energy (or work to fracture absorbed during slow bend testing), especially since total failure of all the wires did not occur throughout any section in these tests.

It may be concluded that the increases in energy absorbed can only be explained in terms of the elimination of compressive buckling failure with a concomitant increase of tensile pullout of fibres and wire, local plastic deformation of the wire or delamination, all of these being higher energy absorbing processes than compressive failure. Where compressive failure occurred in the wire reinforced slow bend specimens, only small increases are noted as the proportion of compressive failure decreases.

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Table I. Fibre and Wire Properties

Fibre or Wire Type	Tensile Modulus (GN/m ⁻²)	Tensile Strength (GN/m ⁻²)	Diameter (um)	Strain to failure %
Carbon type III (untreated)	190*	2.4*	8*	1.1*
Piano Wire	197	2.76	130*	2.6 (1.3% yield strain)
Piano Wire	197	2.16	260*	- (0.9% yield strain)
Rocket Wire	205	3.71	130*	3.6 (1.8% yield strain)

* Values for sample batches provided by manufacturers.

Table II. Composite Properties

Composite Type	V_f^C Carbon Fibres	V_f^S Steel Wires	Interlaminar Shear Stress (I.L.S.S.) (MN/m^2)		Flexural Strength (GN/m^{-2})		Impact Test - Fracture Energy (kJ/m^2)			
							Normal		Transverse	
							Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
HR4C - no wires	0.585	-	58.6	1.7	1.39	0.13	105	18	69	10
HR4C with 0.13 mm piano wire	0.488	0.078	59.9	2.6	1.40	0.09	147	23	113	8
HR4C with 0.25 mm piano wire	0.498	0.077	57.0	1.3	1.44	0.11	165	24	109	12
HR4C with 0.13 mm rocket wire	0.486	0.073	59.9	2.3	1.43	0.14	178	22	130	12

Figure 1. Typical microstructures of plain and wire filled carbon fibre composites.
 a) all carbon fibre (x 100)
 b) $0.08 V_f$ 0.13 mm piano wire (x 50)
 c) $0.08 V_f$ 0.26 mm piano wire (x 60)

Figure 2. Impact energies of plain and 0.08 V_f wire filled carbon fibre composites.

Figure 3. Typical failed impact specimens.
 a) Plain carbon fibre b) 0.13 mm piano wire
 c) 0.13 mm Rocket wire d) 0.26 mm piano wire

Figure 4. Work to fracture of plain and 0.08 V_f wire filled carbon fibre composites from slow bend test.

Figure 5. Slow bend load-displacement plots of wire filled composites showing:
 a) mixed compressive/tensile failure
 b) tensile pullout failure only
 c) tensile pullout and delamination failure.

Figure 6. Typical failed slow bend specimens
 a) mixed compressive/tensile failure
 b) tensile pullout and delamination failure showing unbroken ligament.

a

b

Figure 7. Slow bend fracture surfaces of plain and wire reinforced composites showing regions of compressive failure and tensile pullout failure. a) Plain composite fracture surface, b) Wire reinforced composite fracture surface (note distribution of wires)

Figure 8. Region of tensile pullout failure of slow bend specimen showing "cup and cone" failure of wires.